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ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6142-7054

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ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9313-4918

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ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5409-4327

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кандидат медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Педиатрии,
неонатологии и протекции детских болезней №2
Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523

Ибрагимова Малика Худайбергеновна

доктор медицинских наук, профессор
Ташкентского государственного
стоматологического института
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742

Рахимов Нодир Махамматкулович

доктор медицинских наук, доцент кафедры
онкологии Самаркандского государственного
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Samarkand State Medical University No. 2.
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523*

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*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor,
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ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742*

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*DSc, Associate Professor of Oncology,
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TURAYEV Bobir Temirpulotovich

Assistant

OCHILOV Ulug'bek Usmanovich

PhD

SHARAPOVA Dilfuza Nematillayevna

Clinical ordinator

Samarkand State Medical University

MODERN APPROACHES TO THE DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF ACQUIRED MENTAL RETARDATION, EPIDEMIOLOGY OF DEMENTIA, CLINICAL FORMS (LITERATURE REVIEW)*Corresponding author: Turayev T. Bobir bobir.turaev.89@mail.ru*

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 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10895984>**ANNOTATION**

Objective: to determine the degree of study of clinical forms, diagnosis and treatment of acquired mental retardation, dementia.

Material and methods: more than 40 scientific literature written on dementia has been studied and analyzed.

Results: during the review of the literature, detailed reviews were published about mental retardation, clinical manifestations of dementia and the most common forms of this disease – Alzheimer's disease, Lewy dementia, a typical clinical picture of vascular dementia, and widely covered the issues of effectiveness and safety in the use of NMDA receptor antagonists in patients with this pathology.

Conclusion. Acquired mental retardation, dementia is a disease that has not yet been fully studied and has its own clinical scar. In this study, we examined the methods of modern approaches to the diagnosis and treatment of Alzheimer's disease, Lyu dementia, clinical forms of vascular dementia.

Keywords: dementia, Alzheimer's disease, Lewy body dementia, vascular dementia, cognitive disorders, diagnosis, treatment.

ТУРАЕВ Бобир Темирпулотович

Ассистент

ОЧИЛОВ Улугбек Усманович

PhD

ШАРАПОВА Дилфуза Нематиллаевна

Клиник ординатор
Самаркандский государственный медицинский университет,

СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ К ЭПИДЕМИОЛОГИИ, КЛИНИЧЕСКИМ ФОРМАМ, ДИАГНОСТИКЕ И ЛЕЧЕНИЮ ПРИОБРЕТЕННОЙ УМСТВЕННОЙ ОТСТАЛОСТИ, ДЕМЕНЦИИ (ОБЗОР ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ)

АННОТАЦИЯ

Цель: определить степень изученности клинических форм, методов диагностики и лечения приобретенной умственной отсталости, деменции.

Материал и методы: изучено и проанализировано более 40 наименований научной литературы, написанной по деменции.

Полученные результаты: в ходе обзора литературы подробно рассмотрены приобретенная умственная отсталость, клинические проявления деменции и типичные клинические проявления наиболее распространенных форм этого заболевания – болезни Альцгеймера, деменции Леви, сосудистой деменции, а также широко освещены вопросы эффективности и безопасности применения антагонистов рецепторов НМДА у пациентов с данной патологией.

Выводы. Приобретенная умственная отсталость, деменция-это заболевание, которое еще полностью не изучено и имеет характерные клинические проявления. В этом исследовании мы рассмотрели современные подходы к клиническим формам, диагностике и лечению болезни Альцгеймера, деменции Леви, сосудистой деменции.

Ключевые слова: деменция, болезнь Альцгеймера, деменция с тельцами Леви, сосудистая деменция, когнитивные нарушения, диагностика, лечение.

TURAYEV Bobir Temirpulotovich

Assistent

OCHILOV Ulug'bek Usmanovich

PhD

SHARAPOVA Dilfuza Nematillayevna

Klinik ordinator

Samarqand davlat tibbiyot universiteti, Samarqand, O'zbekiston

ORTIRILGAN AQLIY ZAIFLIK, DEMENSIYANING EPIDEMIOLOGIYASI, KLINIK SHAKLLARI, DIAGNOSTIKASI VA DAVOLASHDA ZAMONAVIY YONDASHUVLAR (ADABIYOTLAR SHARHI)

ANNOTATSIYA

Maqsad: Ortirilgan aqliy zaiflik, demensiya kasalligi klinik shakllari, diagnostikasi va davolash usullarining o'rganilish darajasini aniqlash.

Material va metodlar: Demensiya kasalligi bo'yicha yozilgan 40 dan ortiq ilmiy adabiyot o'rganildi va tahlil qilindi.

Olingan natijalar: Adabiyotlarni ko'rib chiqish davomida ortirilgan aqliy zaiflik, demensiyaning klinik ko'rinishlari va ushbu kasallikning eng keng tarqalgan shakllari – Altsgeymer kasalligi, Lyui demensiyasi, qon tomir demensiyasining tipik klinik ko'rinishi batafsil ko'rib chiqilgan va ushbu patologiyaga ega bemorlarda NMDA retseptorlari antagonistlaridan foydalanish samaradorligi va xavfsizlik masalalari keng yoritilgan.

Xulosa. Ortirilgan aqliy zaiflik, demensiya kasalligi hali to'liq o'rganilmagan va o'ziga xos klinik shakllarga ega bo'lgan kasallikdir. Biz ushbu tadqiqotimizda Altsgeymer kasalligi, Lyui demensiyasi, qon tomir demensiyasining klinik shakllari, diagnostikasi va davolashda zamonaviy yondashuvlar usullarini ko'rib chiqdik.

Kalit so'zlar: demensiya, Altsgeymer kasalligi, Lyui demensiyasi, qon tomir demensiyasi, kognitiv buzilishlar, tashxis, davolash.

Relevance. In psychiatric practice, cognitive disorders are one of the most common pathologies, and usually these pathologies have a significant impact on the way of life of people. According to many scientists, as a result of cognitive fuchsia disorders, people's living conditions and living standards change to varying degrees. When cognitive fuchsia disorders become severe and mental retardation deepens to dementia, patients feel the need for help from those around them and can no longer do what they did before on their own. To date, among the dorzab problems of medicine, cognitive fuchsia pathologies are also included, namely dementia, since preventive measures and methods of early diagnosis of this pathology have not yet been fully studied. It is claimed by scientists all over the world that dementia is being rejuvenated and spread widely among the population, with progressive growth from year to year [1-3].

The increase in cognitive impairment among the population raises many questions about this disease in general practitioner physicians and requires them to have higher knowledge and skills about this disease. Modern books contain a large amount of information on the etiology, pathogenesis, clinical course, treatment, and reabilitation of cognitive disorders[4]. Cognitive fuchsia disorder is one of the characteristics that are usually age-specific and should pay attention to the indivial approach to each person and his previous intellectual potential in diagnosing this pathology. Many theories have put forward the idea that cognitive distortions in humans are related to his previous level of intelligence [5].

To show that cognitive fuchsia disorder in many studies is dependent on generational predisposition and external muhid factors. If these two factors together affect the acceleration of the development of the disease ispodated [6].

The most common of cognitive disorders is Alzheimer's disease, a disease with a high rate of occurrence in individuals who have been mainly involved in mental labor for a long time, have experienced various severe mental trauma throughout their lives, and have a pedigree predisposition [7].

Cognitive disorders are divided into mild, moderately severe, and severe levels according to the severity of the course of most disorders. There has been a slight decrease in memory and attention in people with cognitive impairment, usually at mild levels, and these disorders hardly affect his living conditions and lifestyle. Such people function in society among other people, but in these patients, as time passes, i.e. as they get younger, the disease progresses and boorish sadness increases. Moderately severe form in these patients, a change in almost all elements of cognitive Fuchsia is observed, and patients become isolated from society. The support of those around them for these patients is always zaruz and they have difficulty without their help. This group of patients often loses their personal belongings and searches for them for a long time. Severe form cognitive impairment these patients become completely in need of help from those around them, without their help they cannot even meet their needs [8-10].

In the process of diagnosing cognitive fuchsia disorders, it is necessary that each specialist knows age norms. Most experts have the opinion that memory impairment is a physiological condition of this age. Usually, memory impairment is understood as the degree of acceptance of new information and their implementation in practice. Of course isnsion's ability to master new information will also weaken as he gets older [11].

The determination of cognitive fuchsia disorder for each person is carried out in an individual order. Cognitive disorders are one of the most common pathologies in elderly people, and this pathology impairs patients' ability to adapt to social life. The earliest harbinger of cognitive impairment was memory impairment. Cognitive disorders are usually accompanied by anxious and emotional disorders. Emotional disorders usually manifest as part of cognitive disorders, and this pathology mainly occurs in the early stages of cognitive disorders and can stretch for a long time [12].

Usually in the moderately severe Daja of cognitive impairment, alarming depressive disorder manifests itself to a wide extent and is maintained for a long time. These patients are treated in an outpatient or inpatient setting and require prolonged treatment [13].

Cognitive fuchsia disorders are usually examined in a case where specific neuropsychological tests are used and evaluated to match the indivial age. In addition to neuropsychological tests, their

complaints are also important in this group of patients. Usually these patients cannot find what they put in, often uniting the birthday or names of loved ones, struggling or spending a long time doing what they did before [14].

Many clinical signs are seen as clinical signs of severe cognitive impairment. For example speech disorders in the language of science, they call it Alexia or aphasia. In addition, the impairment of defecation-aproxia, or Korsakov syndrome as an example of severe memory impairment, etc [15].

Differential dignostics of cognitive fuchsia disorder are conducted with pseudodemension, delirium, and other disorders. Usually many doctors have difficulty making differential dignostics with a dilery condition. The main clinical sign of a dealer is a disorder of consciousness in cognitive impairment, a disorder of consciousness is not observed [16].

Pseudodemension exhibits depression and hysteria as the primary clinical simtom, and these simtoms exhibit a similar clinic with cognitive impairment. Patients with pseudodemension will have preserved projection, clock drawing, and Caspian seal [17].

Many specialists have difficulty in differential diagnosis of pseudodemence and dementia. Neuropsychological tests are important in the diagnosis of both of these diseases. In order to diagnose dementia, it is necessary that the few major simtoms that manifest due to morphofoxional or organic changes in the brain are memory, attention, intelligence, reading, writing, counting, and other simtoms. Diagnosis of dementia requires cognitive impairment, cranial organic impairment, impaired ability to work, and the retention of consciousness. The presence of the simtoms listed above provides the basis for the diagnosis of dementia [18].

According to the analysis of scientists, Alzheimer's disease accounts for 35% to 50% of dementia. This disease is increasing from year to year, as scientists insist. Until now, it has not been established why this disease is caused by increased boorish in a progressive form. The main developmental pathogenesis of Alzheimer's disease is the hypothetical hypothesis of the deposition of a toxic amyloid protein into the brain. This protein stimulates the acetylcholinergic domain resulting in an increased denervative process in the cranial brain that causes neuronal death. As a result of these processes, neurodegenerative changes occur in almost all areas of the brain [19].

According to scientists, there is an inextricable relationship between memory disorders observed in Alzheimer's disease and acetylcholinergic insufficiency, at the base of both of these processes lies damage to the cranial neurons. Alzheimer's disease will be diagnosed with dementia in the initial period, and after a certain period, the diagnosis will be made Alzheimer's disease, depending on the results of the neuropsychological test necessary for diagnosis and the degree of manifestation of clinical symptoms [14].

The generational factor plays an important role in the development of Alzheimer's disease. Genetic correlation should be taken into account if patients have dementia in their Anamnesis progeny. Usually the disease manifests itself early if there is a hereditary predisposition. Late-manifestation Alzheimer's disease usually does not depend on procreative predisposition. Late-onset Alzheimer's disease will depend on cardiovascular disease, cranial damage, and other factors [8].

The clinical course of Alzheimer's disease lasts a long time, and early diagnosis of this disease is important for treatment and clinical course. The diagnostic criteria for Alzheimer's disease today include various forms of memory impairment (inability to find what one has put in it and the gradual exacerbation of this condition, inability to complete neuropsychological tests that detect memory impairment), cranial atrophy [11].

In the diagnosis of Alzheimer's disease, it is important to obtain memory impairment as the main simtom. In doing so, it is enough to ask the patient to repeat them by saying a few words or draw a drawing [4].

Insole Lewis dementia, studied by Louis insoles, is also reduced along with cognitive disorders such as Alzheimer's disease, and is manifested by visual hallucinations in contrast to it. Usually hallucinations are true, and cognitive fuchsia manifests itself against the background of a disorder. In patients, attention disorders are intense and extremely disorienting. The patient does not remember the events that took place during the period of illness after recovery. The hallucinations seen do not remain in memory at all [14].

The peculiarity of Lyu dementia is that in this disease, the vegetative nervous system is severely damaged. This has a serious impact on the way patients live and life expectancy. The prevalence of vascular dementia is 10-15% among the population. This pathology is generally considered to be significantly higher in individuals with cardiovascular pathology. The risk is considered high in patients with cerebral arterocyclosis, arterial hypertension and various thromboses. In these patients, cognitive disorders and cases of dementia are observed to varying degrees, depending on whether the disease is acute or chronic [5,6].

Vascular dementia in most cases develops after a stroke cognitive fuchsia disorder is to varying degrees inappropriate. Cognitive disorders in vascular diseases are considered one of the main symptoms, and in vascular dementia this rule is used as a basis [9].

Vascular dementia often occurs when cognitive disorders develop after a stroke and become severely smaller. The degree of severity of this disease is directly related to the localization of the pathological process. Thus, the size of the brain stroke performed and its localization play an important role in the development of cognitive disorders in vascular dementia [11].

According to the course of vascular dementia is similar to Alzheimer's disease, but unlike it is not a memory disorder, it is different from Alzheimer's disease with changes in mental activity, speech, movement. Usually in vascular dementia, symptoms such as apraxia, adinamia, dysphasia, dysfunction of the pelvic organs are manifested. These patients, unlike Alzheimer's disease, manifest not only memory disorders, but also mental activity, decreased thinking and speech fluency, impulsivity, difficulties in mastering new movements [16].

Acute circulatory disorders in the cranial brain usually develop suddenly in the evening, with bad dreams, nausea and other mental changes being shown as the cause. These patients show a mental disorder against the background of derealization, impaired consciousness for a period of time. The rapid recurrence of these conditions causes deep cognitive impairment [1].

In vascular dementia, memory impairment develops suddenly, while in Alzheimer's disease it occurs slowly over a long period of time in a progressivable type. In most cases, it is manifested that the cause of developing memory impairment in the post-stroke period is Alzheimer's disease. Clinical neuropsychological examination or neuropsychological tests are important in the differential diagnosis of these two pathologies [7].

Atrophy of the temporal area of the brain is considered as the main clinical sign of Alzheimer's disease. But this pathological process is not directly related to the severity of Alzheimer's disease. Alzheimer's disease simtom, which is common with acute circulatory disorders of the skull, is cranial atrophy, which is characteristic of both diseases. One of the main causes of cognitive disorders is considered to be a lack of B vitamins, and this pathological process significantly increases the development of depression [19].

The treatment of cognitive fuchsia disorders is considered one of the Doric problems of today's medicine. In the course of treatment, it is imperative to identify the cause that causes this pathology. Pathogenetic treatment of cognitive disorders that develop as a result of vascular dementia is the elimination of vascular disease. To do this, the use of antihypertensive drugs, drugs used for cardiac antithrombocytes, arrhythmias and anticoagulants reduces the development of dementia development cartilage and the development of cognitive disorders [3].

For the pathogenetic treatment of Alzheimer's disease, it is important to diagnose this disease as early as possible. To do this, it is necessary to develop new diagnostic criteria for Alzheimer's disease [6].

It is important to identify vascular risk factors in the development of Alzheimer's disease. Arterial hypertension, diabetes mellitus, hypercholesterolemia and other risk factors increase the cartilage of the development of neurodegeneration against the background of Alzheimer's disease. Thus, the identification of vascular risk factors in the development of Alzheimer's disease significantly facilitates the course of treatment of the disease [12].

Identifying pathogenetic treatment in dementia and eliminating possible causes for the development of cognitive disorders increases the chances of symptomatic therapy. In clinical studies, two groups of symptomatic drugs – acetylcholinesterase inhibitors and NMDA receptor antagonists-

are reliable in reducing the severity of cognitive impairment in the treatment of dementia (Alzheimer's disease, vascular dementia, Lewi insole dementia). The clinical efficacy of the above treatment has been suggested based on an assessment of the dynamics of cognitive impairment in patients, changes in behavior and life adaptation, quality of life [14].

The effectiveness of acetylcholinesterase inhibitors in pathogenetic treatment in dementia is determined by their effect on acetylcholine metabolism in the brain, and the action of NMDA receptor antagonists controls the activity of acetylcholinergic, dopaminergic and noradrenergic systems [6].

The neuroprotective effects of NMDA receptor antagonists are important in the treatment of dementia. This group of drugs helps neurons survive in ischemia conditions.

Discussion.

Cognitive fuchsia disorder is one of the characteristics that are usually characteristic of age, and in the diagnosis of this pathology, an individual approach should be taken to each person. Many theories put forward the idea that cognitive distortions in humans depend on its previous level of intelligence. Cognitive disorders are divided into mild, moderately severe, and severe levels according to severity. There has been a slight decrease in memory and attention in people with cognitive impairment, usually at mild levels, and these disorders hardly affect his living conditions and lifestyle. Such people function in society among other people, but in these patients, as time passes, i.e. as they get younger, the disease progresses and boorish sadness increases. Moderately severe form in these patients, a change in almost all elements of cognitive Fuchsia is observed, and patients become isolated from society. The support of those around them for these patients is always zaruz and they have difficulty without their help. This group of patients often loses their personal belongings and searches for them for a long time. Severe form cognitive impairment these patients become completely in need of help from those around them, without their help they cannot even meet their needs.

There is an inextricable relationship between memory impairment observed in Alzheimer's disease and acetylcholinergic insufficiency, at the base of both of these processes lies damage to the cranial neurons. Lyu dementia is also reduced along with cognitive disorders, such as Alzheimer's disease, and is manifested by visual hallucinations in contrast to it. In patients, attention disorders are intense and extremely disorienting. The patient does not remember the events that took place during the period of illness after recovery. The hallucinations seen do not remain in memory at all. According to the course of vascular dementia is similar to Alzheimer's disease, but unlike it is not a memory disorder, it is different from Alzheimer's disease with changes in mental activity, speech, movement. Usually in vascular dementia, symptoms such as apraxia, adinamia, dysphasia, dysfunction of the pelvic organs are manifested. This mental activity, a decrease in the fluency of thinking and speech, impulsivity, difficulties in mastering new actions are manifested.

Two groups of symptomatic drugs in treatment – acetylcholinesterase inhibitors and NMDA receptor antagonists-are reliable in their effectiveness in reducing the severity of cognitive impairment. In addition, symptomatic therapy and the help of loved ones of patients are also important.

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Информация об авторах:

Тураев Бобир Темирпулотович – ассистент, Самаркандский государственный медицинский университет, Самарканд, Узбекистан. E-mail: bobir.turaev.89@mail.ru
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4748-5327>

Очиллов Улугбек Усманович - PhD, доцент, Самаркандский государственный медицинский университет, Самарканд, Узбекистан. E-mail: ulugbek_o@mail.ru

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3553-8727>

Шарапова Дилфуза Нематиллаевна - клиник ординатор, Самаркандский государственный медицинский университет, Самарканд, Узбекистан. E-mail: dilfuzasharapova@mail.ru

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4963-5678>

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Тураев Б.Т. - идеологическая концепция работы, написание текста; редактирование статьи;

Очилов У.У. - сбор и анализ источников литературы, написание текста.

Шарапова Д.Н. - сбор и анализ источников литературы, написание текста.

Information about the authors:

Turayev Bobir Temirpulotovich assistant, Samarkand State Medical University, Samarkand, Uzbekistan E-mail: bobir.turaev.89@mail.ru <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4748-5327>

Ochilov Ulugbek Usmanovich PhD, Samarkand State Medical University, Samarkand, Uzbekistan E-mail: ulugbek_o@mail.ru <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3553-8727>

Sharapova Dilfuza Nematillayevna Clinical ordenator, Samarkand State Medical University, Samarkand, Uzbekistan E-mail: dilfuzasharapova@mail.ru <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4963-5678>

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Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

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